

in a split-plot design with screening methods as the main plot and varieties as subplots. Treatments were replicated five times.

In the SSST, seeds of BPH-resistant varieties and susceptible check TN1 were sown in rows in seedboxes (60 × 40 × 10 cm). At 7 d after sowing (DAS), seedlings were thinned to 15/row and infested with eight 2d-instar *S. furcifera* nymphs/plant. When all TN1 seedlings were dead, plants were rated for damage on a 0-9 scale where 0-3 = resistant, 4-6 = moderately

resistant, and 7-9 = susceptible.

In the MSST, seeds were sown and seedlings thinned as described for the SSST experiment. Plants were infested with four 2d-instar nymphs/plant at 20 DAS. Damage was rated at 25 d after infestation when TN1 was dead.

In the SSST, insects in the initial infestation killed TN1; in the MSST, the progeny of the infesting insects killed TN1.

There were distinct differences among BPH-resistant varieties in both tests (see

table). Mudgo and IR64 (*Bph 1* gene), Rathu Heenati and IR62 (*Bph 3* gene), Gambada Samba and Babawee (*bph 4* gene), ARC10550 (*bph 5* gene), Swarnalata (*bph 6* gene), and Ptb21 and Ptb33 (*bph 2 + Bph 3* genes) were rated as resistant in both tests. Varieties Ptb18 and IR36 (*bph 2* gene) and IR56 (*Bph 3* gene) were susceptible in the SSST as seedlings, but were highly resistant as the older plants in MSST (see table). ■

Field screening of rice cultivars for resistance to leafhopper (LF)

(*Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée) and stem borer (SB) (*Sesamia inferens* Walker)

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LF and SB can be destructive rice pests in Sikkim. Infestations of LF and SB occur from late Aug through Oct. We observed peak infestation of LF at panicle initiation, the last week of Sep. Yield losses to both pests can be avoided by using resistant varieties.

Twenty-four cultivars with medium to late maturity from around India, including the NEH Region, were transplanted in 2-m² field plots during 1990 and 1991

kharif (monsoon) seasons with three replicates. All recommended crop management practices were followed except plant protection measures. For each entry, we recorded number of hills with LF and SB infestations at panicle initiation and total hills per plot.

Sikre, Khonorullo, Khusaro, RCPL 3-5, and Dhansé were found moderately resistant to LF, 13 cultivars were moderately susceptible, and 6 cultivars were susceptible. Sikre, Srinivasa, IRAT141, Sarassa, and RCPL3-4 were moderately resistant to SB, 15 cultivars were moderately susceptible, and 4 cultivars were susceptible (see table). ■

Screening of rice cultivars for resistance to LF and SB. Sikkim, India, 1990 and 1991 kharif seasons.

Cultivar	LF incidence (% infested hills/plot)			Reaction ^a	SB incidence (% infested hills/plot)			Reaction
	1990	1991	Mean		1990	1991	Mean	
VL 23	23.1	8.3	15.7	S	6.4	3.3	4.9	MS
Nagoba	8.6	9.5	9.0	MS	2.5	2.2	2.4	MS
Sikre	0.0	4.5	2.3	MR	0.0	0.7	0.4	MR
Srinivasa	7.3	10.6	8.9	MS	0.0	3.6	1.8	MR
Zhapara	7.0	10.8	8.9	MS	1.2	4.2	3.3	MS
DR92	11.3	13.6	12.5	S	2.6	12.8	7.7	MS
Khonorullo	0.0	3.1	1.5	MR	7.4	1.6	4.5	MS
TRUA 490	0.0	11.2	5.5	MS	14.1	2.1	8.1	S
IC25697	5.9	2.2	4.1	MS	10.3	7.8	9.0	S
Khusaro	2.0	0.8	1.4	MR	0.0	4.4	2.2	MS
PP2-24-1557	12.3	5.5	8.9	MS	7.0	1.3	4.2	MS
RCPL 3-5	3.2	5.5	4.3	MR	9.5	2.0	5.8	MS
IRAT141	8.0	8.2	8.1	MS	2.3	0.7	1.5	MR
IR36	10.0	5.7	7.9	MS	12.9	14.9	13.9	S
Sarassa	11.3	6.9	9.1	MS	0.0	0.7	0.4	MR
Jaya	16.7	13.3	14.8	S	2.9	9.9	6.4	MS
ICPL 131	4.1	7.6	5.8	MS	3.1	1.5	2.3	MS
Akhanpan	11.1	6.3	8.7	MS	17.5	11.5	14.5	S
ARU3	13.3	7.8	10.6	S	1.1	6.6	3.8	MS
CSR80	17.1	7.8	12.5	S	2.3	3.5	2.9	MS
Attey	4.8	8.2	7.0	MS	1.2	3.4	2.3	MS
Vikash	10.9	4.5	7.7	MS	4.4	3.5	3.9	MS
RCPL 3-4	9.9	9.1	9.5	S	0.0	0.7	0.4	MR
Dhansé	0.0	3.7	1.9	MR	7.2	6.8	7.0	MS

^aMR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, and S = susceptible.

Evaluation of rice genotypes for resistance to orange-headed leafhopper (OHLH) in the Hill Zone of Karnataka, India

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Orange-headed leafhopper (*Thaia subrufa* M., Cicadellidae: Homoptera) is a serious pest of summer rice in the Hill Zone of Karnataka. Feeding by nymphs and adults causes leaves to become speckled. The speckles coalesce when infestation is severe, leading to hopperburn symptoms. Grain losses can range from 30 to 70%.

Rice genotypes were screened for resistance to OHLH in two phases at RRS. We mass-screened 243 varieties in phase one (1986-88). Each entry was planted in three rows with two replica-